

PROBLEMS OF SKILLS OF YOUNG FILMMAKERS IN UZBEK CINEMATOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article examines the achievements and shortcomings of today's directors and actors in the analysis of Uzbek feature films, and makes the necessary suggestions. At the same time, the works of talented actors and cameramen are being considered in Uzbek cinema on the example of director's films. Feature and telenovela films created by our directors are analyzed from the point of view of professionalism. Suggestions and comments will be made to address the existing problems in feature films.

Directing and acting are creative activities directly related to theater and cinema. The director's work requires complete dedication. The director not only carefully selects the script, but also adapts it to his worldview and point of view, that is the way of making a director's script. In this process, he tries to choose the best possible cast of actors, to enhance the image of the film, its true interpretation, to approach each essence individually and in a special way.

Many directors describe their ideas and thoughts in detail, and some, on the contrary, consider improvisation to be the main tool of practical directing.

Naturally, without an actor, the director cannot realize his creative ideas, which are considered the unique fruit of his wealth of thought. Working with the actor is also a main task of the director, and it should be mentioned that this task of his appeared

before the discovery of cinema or television, in the early days of theaters. When an actor plays a certain role, he directs all his skills to get into the image of his character, to express his character and his inner world and feelings. In doing so, he thoroughly studies the content of the script and spends his energy and skills in bringing it to life.

Such actors as A. Khidoyatov, O. Khojaev, Sh. Burkhanov, R. Pirmukhammadov, L. Sarimsokova, Ya. Abdullaeva and so on ... left with bright name not only in the theater, but also in the history of Uzbek film and art. They founded the acting school of Uzbek film.

However, some directors are forgetting the importance of casting before filming. Nowadays, because of the so-called "candy" actors or actresses acting in movie our national cinema quality decreasing significantly.

A. Uzokov in the film "The Last Moment" by the young director A. Bekturdiyev, in 2009, A. Rajabov in the film "Sarvqomat dilbarim" by the director S. Karimov in

2018, and M. Abulkhairov in the film "Oling quda bering quda" by J. Ahmedov are skillfully played their roles. Noteworthy that they performed reliably.

It is commendable that the human feelings, its pain and concerns, people's dreams, love and loyalty to the motherland are glorified in unique words, tones and colors. As our great poet Cholpon said, "We have no right to forget that the nation lives only with literature and culture."

Of course, in any creative process, the director's and the actor's creative thinking, horizon, and attitude towards the work should fully match. That is why it is said that the profession of a director is not only responsible but also comprehensive.

We can clearly say that great directors such as N.Ganiev, K.Yormatov, Y.Azamov, L.Fayziev, E.Eshmukhammedov, A.Khamroev, D.Salimov and Sh.Abbosov, who contributed to the development of Uzbekistan's film industry, have left a golden legacy for the future generation. That's why we have learned cinematography by watching their films and the younger generations are still learning.

Today, the need for a professional director in our country is very great, and this issue is becoming more urgent day by day. Often, some young directors realize how uneducated they are. Among them, there

are even those who have not seen such immortal works as "Tahir and Zuhra" by N.Ganiev, or "Alisher Navoi" by K.Yormatov, and "You are not an orphan" by Sh.Abbasov. At the time of the current development, wide opportunities for self-development and modernization are opened, the work of some young directors surprises. It is difficult to understand how such low-quality films can be filmed at a time when science, technology are developed and the worldview of the audience is expanding and growing. What is the reason for this? My attention was drawn to the opinions expressed by an ordinary viewer far from the cinema domain on the Facebook social network about modern feature films and TV series. He expressed his reaction to the telenovela "Iqror" produced by "Milliy" TV channel. He mockingly talked about the film, its plot, the idea it raises, and its negative impact on the audience, especially on the spiritual world of upbringing generation. He also used some very ugly expressions in his comment and pointed out that there are elements in the plot of this telenovela that do not correspond to ethics and aesthetics of nation and promote obscenity and

depravity. Even a non-specialist viewer clearly proves that this film does not approach even the requirements of ordinary art.

As we all know, there are a lot of different opinions in the internet, there are a lot of negative ones among them. However, there is certainly a serious reason for the emergence of such negative thoughts. It is necessary for a creative person to follow universal, noble ideas. Unfortunately, many "creators" today follow the audience, and the audience teaches them how to make a movie. I believe that lack of knowledge and lack of spirituality is at the root of such low of level.

As our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "Development of literature, art and culture is a solid foundation for raising the spiritual world of our people." By reading at these words, a reasonable question arises whether we artists able to create this solid foundation with the works we are creating today. The great Russian director, actor and pedagogue Konstantin Sergeevich Stanislavsky said in his works: "If the level of the written work is low, no matter how much we decorate the stage, we will not be able to create a good performance from this work." It can be concluded that the foundation of the film is dramaturgy. If the foundation is not strong, neither the director who is a master of his work, nor the talented actors can do

anything, even if it is filmed by a very skilled cameraman, it is useless.¹

As he reads the tragedies of W.Shakespeare and other world's great writers and dramatists and also the comedic works as J.Moller, he gets deeper into his special spiritual world. The spiritual wealth and global ideas of these works are so perfect and deep that it seems impossible to finish the analysis.

The films "Suyunchi", "Abdullajon", "Tangalik boys", "Duel under the maple tree", "The sky is near", "The traitor", "The old man and the grandson", created on the basis of the scripts of the Uzbek screenwriter and film director R. Muhammadjonov are still on our TV screens. If we pay attention to the film "Old Man and Grandson" shot in 2006, the hero of the picture is a seven or eight-year-old boy named Ganisher. The child is very stubborn and restless. The most important person for Ganisher is his grandmother, who walks with him everywhere without leaving a single step behind her. After his mother's death, he becomes even more attached to his grandfather. But, unfortunately, by the will of fate, his grandfather also leaves him forever...

The correct selection of the group of actors in the film, the atmosphere is suitable for the genre, and the thoroughness of the script certainly gave the director ample opportunities to show his skills. In 2009,

¹https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=i_O1s8IAAAAJ&citation_for_view=i_O1s8IAAAAJ:Y0pCki6q_DkCCreative researches of young cameramen on the creation of graphic image in modern uzbek feature films

M Ikboljon, KS Tirkashaliyevich

the very meaningful and educational film "Suv yokalab" directed by J. Kasimov is also worthy of attention. In this film, life events are reflected, and the main character performed by talented actor E.Komilov, has showed that he is the owner of high skills. A. Ganiev's film "Brother" was also warmly received by the audience. The role played by the talented actor U. Kadirov who in the film very convincingly portrayed. The episode of the hero's childish defense of his brother brings tears to our eyes on every time we see it.

Therefore, it would be appropriate if every director fulfills the trust given to him diligently by our country, responsibly and tastefully. Most of our directors spend money to shoot a high quality film. But along with talent, a director should also have the qualities of duty. As the talented

actor, director, screenwriter Ch. Chaplin said: "I need a park, a policeman and one beautiful girl to shoot a comedy." But we know what great works Ch. Chaplin created. It can be seen that the creator does not need much. If one does not burn from the inside for art, it is clear that he cannot burn others.

Operators are responsible for the visual aspect of the movie. The reason is that an untalented operator can completely destroy the idea of the screenwriter, the work of the director, actor, artist and many other specialists. The task of the operator is extremely difficult. Nowadays, we have a lot of cinematographers who are creating from a professional point of view in their field. Examples of this are H.Hasanov, I.Meliko'ziev, A. Arzikulov, R. Murodov, etc.

The development of society cannot be imagined without art. Because humanity cannot live without art, just as he cannot live outside of society. The role of art in enriching the spiritual world of every person and forming aesthetic taste is unique.²

Since time immemorial, our people have treated the people of creativity with great respect and trust. Let's not lose the trust of our people. Because the God himself has given such a unique talent and potential to the tenant, not everyone has such a characteristic, such a virtue.

As our honorable president Sh.M.Mirziyoev said: "If we do not write about such builders and engineers, field workers who are the true heroes of our time, about the achievements and milestones achieved by our passionate teachers and doctors, our brave soldiers, and our modern youth, if you do not create an artistic chronicle of the history of our country, who will create all of them? If we don't mobilize our talents and skills for this holy land and our noble people, as Hazrat Navoi said, what will we do to preserve this craft, where will we take it?"

Yes, of course, at a time when all the conditions for the development of film art are created, we need to use these conditions effectively. Currently, the

demand of the times requires the creation of films that touch the hearts of the audience. The reason is that among the art forms, film ranks higher than other art forms in terms of its level of influence, strong educational value and popularity.

²https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=i_O1s8IAAAAJ&citation_for_view=i_O1s8IAAAAJ:4JMBOYKVnVMCЎШ АВЛОД РЕЖИССЁРЛАРИНИНГ КИНО САНЪАТИДА ИЖОДИ ВА МАҲОРАТ МАСАЛАЛАРИ

ИМ Мелиқўзиев

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